

Conductometric Analysis of the Process of Coagulation of Ferric Vanadate Sol at its Different States of Purity

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The process of coagulation of ferric vanadate sol at different stages of dialysis was investigated by observing the changes that occur in specific conductivity of the sol during coagulation with the stepwise addition of K_2SO_4 in the increasing order of concentration. Experimental work with even well dialysed sols has shown that there is a regular decrease of the conductivity of the sol (micellar and intermicellar) with the electrolyte addition. Ion exchange is a remote reason for this. Instead, causes due to antagonistic effect, aggregation gelation and salt effects have been described.

The electrical conductance of a sol may be considered as a sum total of micellar conductivity and that arising from the intermicellar liquid. Several workers¹⁻⁴ have used the conductivity determinations to evaluate the exchange of ions between the double layer and the intermicellar liquid. The specific conductivity of As_2S_3 sol itself without that of its corresponding intermicellar liquid was found by Chaturvedi and Bhattacharya⁵ to increase with the addition of an electrolyte. Rai and Ghosh⁶ on the contrary found that the conductivity in excess of the added electrolyte decreased when K_2SO_4 was added progressively to $Fe(OH)_3$ sols. In their studies with the slow coagulation of ferric, chromium and aluminium tellurate sols, and zinc ferrocyanide sol Chaturvedi⁷, Singh and Bansal⁸ observed that the micellar conductivity of the sols changed abruptly indicating thereby that ion-exchange, adsorption, and surface neutralization were instantaneous processes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric vanadate sol was prepared by the usual method as described elsewhere⁹, and sols of different grades of purity were obtained by dialyzing the sol over a span of thirteen days. The composition and the relative purity (expressed in reciprocal coagulation value of K_2SO_4 for the sols) at various stages of dialysis has been shown in table 1. A volume of 10 ml. of the sol of a particular purity was placed in several pyrex glass boiling tubes. To each of these, a constant volume of 10 ml of the electrolyte (K_2SO_4) arranged in a series of regular increasing order of concentration, was added so that the total volume of the sol-electrolyte mixture remained 20 ml. The range of the electrolyte series was so adjusted that coagulation concentration of the electrolyte for the sol was included somewhere in the middle of the series. A separate set of the electrolyte of the identical concentrations was also arranged to which water was added in place of the sol. The mixtures thus prepared were kept in a thermostat bath at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, and the specific conductivities of the mixture

of sol+electrolyte (K_1) and those of the electrolyte alone (K_2) were determined after a lapse of 30 minutes. The ($K_1 - K_2$) value was regarded as the conductivity of the sol itself and the same was plotted as a function of electrolyte concentration for each sol.

TABLE 1

Days of Dialysis	Amt. in gms./lit. of :			Coagulation value (K_2SO_4) milli moles	Reciprocal Coagulation value	Relative Purity
	Fe_2O_3	Cl^-	VO_4^{3-}			
Sol I : 1	19.501	13.550	9.021	36.000	0.0277	0.030
Sol II : 4	11.310	8.333	6.052	16.500	0.0606	0.067
Sol III : 7	9.204	6.110	4.621	9.905	0.1009	0.112
Sol IV : 10	8.000	5.450	3.811	2.775	0.3604	0.400
Sol V : 13	7.521	5.200	3.605	1.112	0.8992	1.000

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 indicates that the sols are progressively deprived of conductivity with the addition of increasing amounts of the electrolyte in a stepwise manner. These results are again contrary to the findings of Chaturvedi and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*) and other workers¹. In the present case the particles of positively charged ferric vanadate hold Cl^- as counter ions. The contribution of Cl^- ions towards conductivity will be small for that part of the ions near the wall and larger to the periphery of the double layer because of the difference which exists, in the mobility of the same ion under the two environments. In the case of As_2S_3

Fig 1. Conductometric titrations of Ferric Vanadate sol at various stages of dialysis.

sol, H^+ ions form the counter ions. Addition of the electrolyte should displace the captive H^+ from the Stern. Mukherjee layer to the high mobility region (periphery of the double layer and the intermicellar liquid) and cause the increase in conductivity. Indeed this accounts for the observed conductivity increase in the sols of acidoid type. Applying the same criterion to the sol under investigation, it is futile to arrive at any conclusion, since the conductivity difference, in the ion exchange phenomena between Cl^- and $\frac{1}{2} SO_4^{=}$, is negligible. Other effects such as those described below may be responsible for such conductivity decrease.

When an electrolyte such as K_2SO_4 , is added to the positively charged ferric vanadate sol, chloride ions are displaced to a certain extent from the Stern-S. Mukherjee layer, and sulphate ions get crowded up near the inner layer. The width of the double layer is diminished which results in the decrease of the surface potential and therein of the mobility of the micelles. Secondly, with the gradual addition of the electrolyte upto a certain concentration below that of precipitation concentration, an antagonistic state towards coagulation arises in the system to the effect that the partially neutralized surface of the sol particles fix up some available hydrogen ions by supplementary adsorption so as to restore the positive charge. The arrest of such highly mobile ions should, therefore, cause a decrease in the conductivity values. At and beyond the concentration zone of the rapid coagulation, the micelles become too sluggish with regard to mobility (because of increased radius) which

TABLE II

Specific Conductivity of Ferric Vanadate sol in terms of $(K_1 - K_2)$ value with the stepwise addition of K_2SO_4

Volume of K_2SO_4 (ml.) added to 10 ml. sol. Total volume 20 ml.	$(K_1 - K_2) \times 10^{-3}$ mhos				
	Sol I with M/7 K_2SO_4	Sol II with M/15 K_2SO_4	Sol III with M/30 K_2SO_4	Sol IV with M/90 K_2SO_4	Sol V with M/180 K_2SO_4
0	2.8000	1.3200	0.6600	0.2400	0.0600
1	2.7400	1.2850	0.6400	0.2300	0.0618
2	2.6400	1.2240	0.6080	0.2220	0.0508
3	2.5600	1.1810	0.5750	0.2100	0.0422
4	2.4700	1.1270	0.5440	0.2073	0.0440
5	2.3910	1.0820	0.5160	0.1905	0.0364
6	2.3100	1.0310	0.4740	0.1852	0.0352
7	2.2300	0.9710	0.4580	0.1788	0.0345
8	2.1500	0.9230	0.4100	0.1723	0.0332
9	2.0700	0.8740	0.3810	0.1534	0.0307
10	1.9800	0.8100	0.3430	0.1400	0.0288

K_1 = specific conductivity of the sol + electrolyte

K_2 = specific conductivity of the electrolyte alone

should decrease the conductivity further. Moreover, the formation of jellies specially in the purer varieties, which has been observed with this sol particularly, during the coagulation might be resulting in the entrainment of small amounts of the intermicellar liquid which would otherwise contribute to conductivity. Lastly the salt effect¹⁰, though not pronounced in the present case, should deviate the additivity behaviour of mixed systems towards lesser values of conductivity.

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